

THE CURRENT STATE OF TRADE RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND THE CIS COUNTRIES

Lochinbek Pardayev

TerDU, teacher of the Department of Economics and management

Abstract: foreign trade relations are one of the main branches of the country's development, and this network is directly related to the solution of social, economic and political problems of the development of society. The fact that the countries close to each other conduct trade relations economically is considered in this article. It is especially important to analyze the composition of export imports of countries carrying out mutual trade relations and to increase the share of finished products in the structure of trade relations.

Keywords: Export, import, diversification, foreign trade, resource, commodity, integration

Introduction.

In recent years, Uzbekistan and CIS countries are one of the countries actively participating in World Economic Relations. The fact that the countries have rich reserves of basic types of resources, are located at the intersection of important trade and transport routes, ensuring internal stability in the country and other factors do not adversely affect the trade and economic relations of the republics, but also have a positive impact. Trade and economic relations between Uzbekistan and the CIS have changed in terms of quality and quantity in the years of independence. In its structural structure, changes were made to suit the needs of the national economy. At the same time, there are still some unused opportunities and potential, it is necessary to use them as efficiently as possible. The integration into the world economic system by increasing the efficiency of foreign trade, diversifying the composition of exports and improving the composition of imports is considered one of the main directions of the countries' foreign economic policy, which is primarily explained by the fact that the current state of the country's foreign trade does not give an opportunity to receive

One aspect of the composition of exports, the priority role of the commodity of raw materials in it, the tightness of the assortment of exported goods makes the economy of the countries dependent on the changes in the world markets

Literature review

A number of scientists of foreign and local economists conducted scientific research on foreign trade relations and on the creation of the conceptual framework of international trade theories, rules and conclusions that affect mutual trade relations.

The essence of international trade and the factors affecting it, the impact of foreign economic activity on the development of the national economy, theoretical and methodological aspects of export policy and foreign trade strategies foreign Economist-scientists-A. Smith, D. Ricardo, E.Heksher, B.Take It, V. Leontev, P. Samuelson, R. Vernon, M. Porter, J. Sex, E. Marshall, P. Krugman, D. Xiks, Dj. M. Keys, F. Deeply studied by Hayek and others.

The peculiarities of foreign trade in the conditions of transition to market relations, theoretical and practical problems of integration of national farms into the world economy, the role of increasing export potential in ensuring sustainable economic growth, scientists of the CIS-V.I.Famichev, I.V. Gagushkina, M.S. Your Landlord, E.P. Report This Website Dabravki, E.F. Avdagushin, L.I. Ebelkin, J.M.Edilav, A.Amriev, A.V.Ibrahimov, I.No, it's not. Benke, and others are reflected in Scientific Research[1].

The main directions of integration of Uzbekistan into the world economic system, scientific-practical aspects of development of foreign economic activity of the country, opportunities to increase export potential of the economists of the Republic – N.Sirajiddinov, A.V V Vakhabov, A.M.Alimov, T.M.Ahmedov, SH.Arifkhanov, A. Sh. Bekmuradov, A.K.Bedrinsev, A.Isadjonov, V.V.Cindalov, E.X.Maxmudov, A.F.Rasulov, E.F.Trushin, N.T.To " khliev, SH.J.Ermamatov F.X.Khakimov, N.B.Xalmatov, R.X.SHodiey, B.Ergashev, A.S.Widely covered in the scientific work of Yusupov and others[2].

Research methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the article is the method of dialectical analysis, and its scientific and cognitive abilities make it possible to analyze foreign trade relations. The methods used in the article do not exclude the possibility of a simple statement of the necessary evidence, which in some cases has the power of evidence and reveals the characteristics of the subject under study.

The study is based on the achievements of economic and other sciences, the works of foreign and Uzbek scientists on the legislation of Economic Sciences, the analysis of trade relations, the current legislation and practice on mutual trade.

Analysis and discussion of results

It is worth noting that the diversification of the composition of foreign trade is carried out in two directions: first, the diversification of the geographical composition of foreign trade, and secondly, the improvement of its composition of goods.

Uzbekistan has achieved significant numbers and quality indicators in foreign trade, including positive changes in the structure of export and import goods. In 1991-2015, the following changes occurred in the structure of foreign trade goods:

1. The share of cotton fiber in exports decreased, leading position in exports decreased. If in 1991 year the share of cotton fiber in total exports amounted to 53.7% in 2015 was 10%.

2. The share of energy resources and petroleum products group in exports has increased. In 2015, 26% of exports accounted for the volume of this group.

3. The share of services exports grew. In 1995, it decreased by 7.7%, 2005 by 12.2% and 2015 by about 3.3%.

4. The share of finished products with high added value in the structure of exports is growing. Currently, the share of non-raw materials in the total volume of exports is more than 70%.

5. The level of diversification of export composition is growing. In particular, products such as automobiles, textile products, mineral fertilizers, building materials, fruits and vegetables have grown exponentially.

6. In connection with the technical and technological modernization of production, it occupies a significant part of the export of machinery and equipment. In 2010-2015, an average of 42% of imports accounted for the contribution of these goods[1].

There have also been positive changes in the structure of export goods with the CIS countries of Uzbekistan. The purposeful development of trade and economic relations of the Republic with the CIS countries is closely connected with the improvement of its brand structure. Analysis shows that foreign trade relations of Uzbekistan with CIS countries play an important role (Table 1).

The foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the CIS countries(bln.the \$.)

№	Countries	Foreign trade turnover	Export	Import
1	Rossiya Federasiyasi	5,6	1,5	4,1
2	Qozog‘iston	3	0,9	2,1
3	Qirg‘iziston	0,9	0,7	0,2
4	Turkmaniston	0,52	0,12	0,4
5	Tojikiston	0,5	0,4	0,1
6	Belorussiya	0,25	0,05	0,2
7	Ozorbayjon	0,08	0,05	0,03
8	Ukraina	0,43	0,12	0,41
9	Moldova	0,012	0,008	0,004
10	Armaniston	0,07	0,04	0,03

In 1992, the Republic of Uzbekistan became a member of the CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States). The foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the CIS countries amounted to 11 830.0 million Manats in January-December 2020. It amounted to US dollars. Exports from it - 4 098.3 million US dollars. If it reached the US dollar, imports – 7 731,7 million. It was recorded in US dollars.

The highest volume of foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan with CIS countries is the Russian Federation (47.7%), Kazakhstan

(25,5 %), Kyrgyz Republic (7,6 %), Turkmenistan (4,5 %) and Tajikistan (4,2 %) were recorded with the countries[3]

Dynamics of volumes of CIS countries and other foreign countries in the foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Picture 1

A third of the foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan accounts for the contribution of CIS countries, and this indicator has changed slightly in recent years

Despite the measures taken to support foreign trade in our republic and further strengthen cooperation with CIS countries in this sphere, the share of CIS countries in the foreign trade turnover for 2020 amounted to 32.6%, and the share of foreign trade turnover in comparison with 2019 decreased by 2.0%.

The share of Uzbekistan in the volume of exports and total exports to CIS countries (in percent)

Picture 2

In the last three years, the overall exhibition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the CIS countries has decreased by almost 8% compared to 2019, while the contribution of other foreign countries has remained virtually unchanged. While Uzbekistan's exports to the CIS amounted to 35.8 percent of total exports in 2018, in 2020 this figure was 27 percent (figure 3). [2]

At the end of 2020, the countries of the PRC (12,8% of the total volume of exports), the Russian Federation (9,7%), Turkey (6,7%), Kazakhstan (6,0%), Afghanistan (5,1%), the Kyrgyz Republic (5,0 %) and Tajikistan (2,7 %) are preserved as part of the main partner Giants in terms of exports of goods and services and their share in total exports is 48.0%.

The share of Uzbekistan in the total volume of imports to CIS countries (in percent)

Picture 3

The share of CIS countries in the import of our country has a lower share than in exports. The bulk of the imported goods accounts for the contribution of far abroad. While the share of imported products from the CIS countries of Uzbekistan accounted for 36,7% in 2019, by 2020 this indicator decreased compared to 36,5% (Figure 3)[4].the share of imported products from the CIS countries was 36,7% in 2019.

Uzbekistan and the CIS countries provide an opportunity to distinguish the following features about the current state of mutual trade relations.

The CIS countries are the main trading partners of Uzbekistan. Factors such as geographic proximity, historically formed economic and cultural ties, economic and transport links in terms of communication are an important basis for the development of trade relations with this country.

Further development of trade and economic relations with the CIS countries the export of products produced in our country to a large-scale market, productive use of the transit potential of this country in the conduct of trade relations with other foreign countries, makes it possible to use the raw material resources of these countries.

The CIS countries are considered the main trading partner of Uzbekistan, and the main part of the foreign trade turnover of Uzbekistan corresponds to the contribution of the CIS countries. Although mutual trade relations have achieved positive indicators

in terms of number and quality over the past period, it can be seen that the share of resource-intensive and low-tech goods is higher than the share of medium and high-tech goods, if the commodity composition of exports is analyzed by the degree of complexity in terms of technology.

The conjuncture of the global raw materials market is non-destructive in contrast to the market of finished products, and the rate of fluctuations in it is considered high. The main reason for this is that the demand for raw materials by price and income is low in elasticity. Therefore, this situation can have a negative impact on macroeconomic stability and economic growth rates. In the value of raw materials, the added value is lower than in finished products. Proceeding from this, it can be said that the pursuit of sustainable economic growth and improving the living conditions of the population can be achieved through deep structural changes in the economy, as well as increasing the share of finished products in the structure of the goods being produced and exported.

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